

CONSTRUCTION AND ARCHITECTURE

ІНСТРУМЕНТАРІЙ ГЕОПРОСТОРОВОГО МОНІТОРИНГУ ВИКОРИСТАННЯ ЗЕМЕЛЬ ЖИТЛОВОЇ ТА ГРОМАДСЬКОЇ ЗАБУДОВИ РЕГІОНІВ

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TOOLS FOR GEOSPATIAL MONITORING OF LAND USE FOR RESIDENTIAL AND PUBLIC BUILDINGS IN REGIONS

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Анотація

Актуальність теми дослідження обумовлена необхідністю формування й застосування інструментарію геопросторового моніторингу використання земель житлової та громадської забудови регіонів.

Запропоновано визначення геопросторового моніторингу використання земель житлової й громадської забудови регіонів як системної категорії, що характеризується сукупністю функціональних, типологічних, інструментальних, інформаційних, оцінних, геоінформаційних, організаційних напрямів, та визначається впливом просторового, екологічного, містобудівного, нормативно-правового забезпечення й спрямований на перманентне відстеження та контролю за змінами, що відбуваються у системі земельних відносин у сфері житлової й громадської забудови.

Abstract

The relevance of the research topic is determined by the need to develop and apply tools for geospatial monitoring of land use for residential and public buildings in regions.

It is proposed to define geospatial monitoring of land use for residential and public development in regions as a systemic category characterised by a set of functional, typological, instrumental, informational, evaluative, geoinformation, and organisational directions, and determined by the influence of spatial, environmental, urban planning, and regulatory and legal support, and is aimed at permanent tracking and control of changes occurring in the system of land relations in the field of residential and public development.

Ключові слова: геопросторовий моніторинг, геоінформаційні системи, використання земель, землі житлової та громадської забудови, методи і моделі.

Keywords: geospatial monitoring, geoinformation systems, land use, residential and public development land, methods and models.

Introduction. Ensuring the efficient use of land is an important task for the development of regions and the state, which shapes the national wealth of the country. In European countries, on average, the structure of land use is determined by its largest implementation in agriculture (43.5% of the total level of land use). Forestry, recreational and residential, industrial and other land use in the European Union accounts for 32.4%, 5.7%, 3.4% and 15.0%, respectively [1]. The European countries with the highest agricultural land use are: Belgium – 51.8%; Great Britain – 63.5%; Denmark – 63.9%; Ireland – 71.5%; Lithuania – 52.9%; Luxembourg – 51.1; Netherlands – 56.9; Germany – 52.0; Poland – 51.6; Romania – 60.3; Hungary – 61.8; France – 54.0; Czech Republic – 50.2 [1]. The land area of Ukraine is almost 6% of that of Europe. At the same time, black soil reserves in this context are estimated at 33.3%. The share of land area in Ukraine compared to European countries and the area of arable land is 9% and 11.7%, respectively. The analysis presented indicates the growing importance of rural land use in European Union countries. Ukraine has a high level of black soil and the intensity of land use is increasing. However, the land market is not fully developed and is rudimentary in nature, with the cost of land resources being the lowest among European countries.

Land for residential and public development accounts for a significant share of the total structure. Problematic aspects of land use, the efficiency of land allocation and development, and the possibilities for taking into account environmental, urban planning and other parameters are highlighted.

In this context, there is a need to apply European experience in land use, using geospatial monitoring (GM) tools for land use (LU) for residential and public development at the regional level. Therefore, the research topic is relevant and timely.

Literature Review. Existing scientific research lacks a unified approach to defining geospatial monitoring of land use. As a result of systematising theoretical approaches to substantiating land use monitoring, a definition has been proposed that is characterised by a combination of legal, constructive, complex, organisational, functional and instrumental directions aimed at forming information, analytical and spatial support regarding the state and level of land and natural resource use with the application of mathematical modelling methods, which creates a quantitative basis for permanent tracking and control of the use of natural reserve fund objects [2].

Land monitoring is characterised from the point of view of functional features and parameters, which is

aimed at observing the state of land for the timely detection of changes, their assessment, prevention and elimination of negative phenomena [3].

Land monitoring is defined as an important functional tool for the systematic collection and updating of information on the state and use of land resources for the implementation of measures for their use and protection [4].

The areas of application of geospatial support for land use monitoring have been identified. Particular attention is focused on the application of geographic information systems [5].

Comprehensive characteristics of land use monitoring have been identified [6, 7].

Characterising the classification features of LU, the factors influencing its development and use have been identified: external: socio-economic; legal; political; technical; territorial; internal: organisational; production and technical; financial [8].

A functional approach to defining land monitoring, which characterises the directions and features of its implementation, is presented in works [9, 10].

For the implementation of LU, within the framework of the instrumental approach, its definition is characterised from the point of view of the application of a system of technical and technological components and the level of use of geographic information systems [8].

As a result of the generalisation of theoretical provisions, the following approaches to the definition of geospatial monitoring of land use for residential and public development are justified:

- functional: characterised by the directions and features of the application of monitoring procedures in the system of land use for residential and public development;
- typological: the structural components of monitoring and types of residential and public development are determined to form a quantitative basis for monitoring;
- factorial: the focus is on identifying factors that influence the implementation of geospatial monitoring of land use for residential and public development;
- instrumental: technological and instrumental aspects of the functioning of geospatial monitoring of residential and public land use are identified and characterised;
- informational: information support for geospatial monitoring of land use is identified and characterised;
- systemic: GM is considered as a complex system in which a set of elements interact;

- evaluative: directions for assessing the level of application of geospatial monitoring of land use for residential and public development are developed and characterised;
- geoinformation: the significance and possibilities of applying geoinformation systems for monitoring procedures are determined;
- stakeholder: the level of interaction and influence of stakeholders on the implementation of geospatial monitoring of land use for residential and public development is characterised;
- organisational: the organisational aspects of the formation and application of geospatial monitoring of land use for residential and public development are determined;
- ecological: focuses on environmental factors that influence the formation and application of GIS;
- regulatory and legal: characterised by regulatory and legislative support for the formation and application of geospatial monitoring of land use for residential and public development;
- urban planning: urban planning factors influencing the formation and application of GIS for residential and public development are identified.

Thus, it is proposed to define geospatial monitoring of land use for residential and public development in regions as a systemic category characterised by a combination of functional, typological, instrumental, informational, evaluative, geoinformation, and organisational aspects, and is determined by the influence of spatial, environmental, urban planning, and regulatory and legal support, and is aimed at permanent monitoring and control of changes occurring in the system of land relations in the field of residential and public development.

At the same time, issues remain unresolved regarding the formation and application of geo-ecological monitoring of the use of land for public and residential development at the regional level.

Purpose and objectives of the study. The purpose of the study is to substantiate the tools for geo-ecological monitoring of land use for public and residential development at the regional level. To achieve this goal, the following tasks are to be accomplished:

- substantiation of models for geospatial monitoring of land use;
- identification of methods that influence the formation of GM LU.

Main part. The directions for the formation and use of geo-ecological monitoring of land use are determined:

1. Modelling of summary indicators.
2. Creation of a geodatabase of land use indicators.
3. Selection of a spatial basis and linking of defined indicators.
4. Distribution of zones for the formation of integrated and summary indicators of land use by region.
5. Analysis of integrated and summary indicators.
6. Visual representation of the analysis data for integrated and summary indicators on a monitoring GIS map.
7. Formation of a spatial basis for the indicator of change in gross regional product per unit area.

8. Construction of a monitoring GIS map of the indicator of change in gross regional product per unit area.

9. Development of a monitoring GIS map of forecast values of the indicator of change in gross regional product per unit area depending on changes in the integral factor of land use.

The method of geoinformation monitoring at the regional level includes: formation of remote sensing data; ground monitoring; preliminary processing of remote sensing data; processing of operational observation data; processing of archived observation data; conducting geospatial analysis and modelling; data presentation; data storage; interaction with users [11].

Regional GIS models have been developed based on the use of geoinformation tools [12, 13].

To carry out geospatial monitoring of land use for residential and public development, a quantitative basis is formed based on methods for assessing land use factors and the results of mathematical modelling.

An integrated method for assessing the territorial development of land use, which includes the following stages:

1. Formation of a complex of spatial, urban planning, investment and environmental factors that influence the territorial development of land use in the region based on existing scientific and methodological developments and regulatory and legal support.

2. Construction of a multi-level system of factors.

3. Selection of factors that most influence the territorial development of land use in the region by applying the expert assessment method.

4. Formation of a multi-level system of indicators by applying quasi-metric methods of transition from the proposed factors to the corresponding spatial, urban planning, investment and environmental indicators, taking into account the values of the assessment coefficients.

5. Evaluation of the system of spatial, urban planning, investment and environmental indicators of the third level based on the application of analytical and expert assessment methods.

6. Determination of second-level spatial, urban planning, investment and environmental indicators by constructing mathematical models based on the method of evaluating the geometric mean.

7. Construction of a mathematical model for determining the integral spatial, urban planning, investment and environmental indicators of territorial development of land use in the region.

8. Determination of weight coefficients characterising the importance of spatial, urban planning, investment and environmental indicators in the system of territorial development of land use in the region based on the application of the hierarchy analysis method.

9. Determination of integral spatial, urban planning, investment, and environmental indicators of territorial development of land use in the region.

10. Assessment of the integral indicator of land use in the region.

11. Development and justification of a scale of levels of territorial development of land use in the region.

12. Interpretation of the results obtained [14].

Mathematical modelling methods for forming a quantitative basis for geospatial monitoring of land use for residential and public development include the following areas:

- forming information and analytical support for mathematical modelling;
- determining the level of influence of factors on the generalising criterion for the development and use of geospatial monitoring of land use for residential and public development;
- development of mathematical models that characterise the cause-and-effect relationships between factors;
- determination of the adequacy criteria for the developed mathematical models;
- interpretation of the results obtained.

The formation of information and analytical support for mathematical modelling is carried out on the basis of a preliminary assessment of factors and a generalising factor of the level of development and use of geospatial monitoring of land use for residential and public buildings.

The level of influence of factors on the generalising criterion is determined on the basis of correlation (R) and determination (D) coefficients. The correlation coefficient is determined using the Statistica software package and shows the degree of influence of factors on the generalising criterion. The value of the coefficient varies from -1 to 1 , and the sign characterises the type of relationship: direct or inverse. If the value of the correlation coefficient approaches 1 , the influence of the factors on the generalising criterion increases accordingly, and vice versa.

The coefficient of determination is determined by the model:

$$D = R^2. \quad (1)$$

The development of mathematical models characterising the cause-and-effect relationships between factors is carried out taking into account the influence, type of relationship, and determined regression coefficients in linear and nonlinear form.

The criteria for the adequacy of the developed mathematical models are as follows:

Student's t-test characterises the quality of the established cause-and-effect relationships. The calculated value of the presented criterion is compared with the normative (tabular) value. If the value of the calculated indicator exceeds the normative value, the quality of the established relationships is confirmed; if not, the factor is excluded from the mathematical model and the established relationships are inadequate.

Fisher's F-criterion shows the significance of the established cause-and-effect relationships. The determined value of the presented criterion is compared with the normative (tabular) value. If the value of the actual indicator exceeds the tabular value, then the conclusion is made about the significance of the established cause-and-effect relationships. If the actual value of Fisher's F-criterion is less than the normative value, then the mathematical model is inadequate and cannot be used to form a quantitative basis for geospatial monitoring

of the use of land for residential and public development.

The Durbin-Watson criterion is used to determine the autocorrelation of residuals, its value varies according to the minimum and maximum values. If the actual value of this criterion is less than the minimum normative value, then the positive autocorrelation of residuals is confirmed. If the actual value exceeds the maximum normative value within the range of criterion values, then there is no autocorrelation of residuals. If the actual value is between the minimum and maximum normative values, it is impossible to conclude whether autocorrelation is present or absent.

Testing for homoscedasticity or heteroscedasticity (homogeneity or heterogeneity of residuals). This is done on the basis of the relevant criteria. In particular, Spearman's criterion is applied and its actual value is compared with the normative value of Student's t-criterion. If the actual value of Spearman's criterion exceeds the normative value of Student's t-criterion, then a conclusion is made about the heterogeneity of the residuals of the mathematical model. If the actual value of Spearman's criterion is lower than the normative value of Student's t-criterion, the homogeneity of the residuals is established and a conclusion is made about the adequacy of the mathematical model.

Checking the mathematical model for multicollinearity, which is carried out for multifactorial mathematical models. The phenomenon of multicollinearity characterises the degree of relationships between independent variables. A high level of multicollinearity leads to a shift in the modelling results and increases the level of inadequacy of the established relationships.

Conclusions. Thus, the proposed methods and models for the formation and use of a quantitative basis for the development of GM LU for residential and public buildings in regions. This provides opportunities to improve the modelling and forecasting system in the context of making informed decisions to improve the efficiency of land use in the field of residential and public buildings.

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